

The mediating role of consumers' perception of atmosphere on emotions and behavior.

A study to analyze the impact of lighting in food retailing

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Abstract: This paper focuses on the influence of a store's environment on consumers' perception of atmosphere, experienced emotions and behavior. We describe an experiment in which we manipulate lighting, as one aspect of the environment, in a three-dimensional simulated lab supermarket. Three different lighting settings, corresponding to three different supermarkets in Belgium, were implemented in a simulated store, while participants were observed during their shopping task and were questioned regarding their mood, emotions, and perceptions such as perceived atmosphere quality level. The results show that the lighting setting in a retail environment can indeed affect the perceived atmosphere and can even result in a correct identification of the real-life setting on which it was based. Moreover, the type of feelings brought about by the store, i.e., a positive versus a negative emotional response, was shown to be linked to the perceived atmosphere, although little difference in behavioral response was found. It appears that even with only a relatively subtle difference in lighting, an otherwise identical supermarket environment can be given a different, or even very specific, atmosphere.

Key words: *Retail design, Lighting, Consumer emotions, 3D-supermarket lab.*

1. Introduction

In today's economy, creating a unique environment becomes a necessity for customer binding and differentiation because the actual merchandise of competitive retailers is often perceived as similar, and no longer as the distinguishing feature between them. This differentiation trend, together with global economic changes and shopping behavior of consumers shifting towards a more hedonic experience, has led to a different, more research-based approach in retail design. Indeed, during the last two decades, interest in the design of commercial environments has steadily increased and was strengthened by empirical studies on the impact of a store environment on its consumers. For example, it has been shown that shop environments can create 'retail experiences' that actually influence consumer's purchasing behavior [see e.g., 1-3] and that the store environment is a key element for image building and creating store personality [4,5].

Although retail design should of course take into account the needs of both the retailers and the consumers, the

focus of this paper is on the consumers. Due to the shift in our economy, they are no longer seen as only buyers of products, but as customers with specific personalities, feelings and longings. This implies that it is of great importance for retailers, retail designers and researchers to try to understand how consumers actually perceive, interpret and respond, both emotionally and physically, to specific aspects of a retail environment. Here, we try to investigate this process using the conceptual framework presented in Figure 1 (see [6] for more detailed information). More specifically, we use this model to look at how changing a store's atmosphere through lighting affects the consumer.

Figure.1 Conceptual research model, based on the S-O-R of Donovan and Rossiter [7]

We focus on the atmosphere, with lighting as one aspect of it, because its impact on the environment is relatively high, while at the same time it can be relatively easily manipulated. Therefore, how atmosphere is perceived in the context of a retail environment and how it makes the consumer feel are the first objectives of this paper. In addition, we also investigate the possible effects of the retail environment on actual shopping behavior.

2. Organism

In an S-O-R model such as our conceptual research model, the 'organism' refers to "the internal processes and structures intervening between stimuli external to the person and the final actions, reactions, or responses emitted. Notice that the intervening processes and structures consist of perceptual, physiological, feeling and thinking activities" [8, p. 46]. Simplified: we assume that the effect of store environmental cues (S) – whether they are aesthetical, atmospherical or functional – on final consumer behavior (R) is mediated by the consumer's internal state (O). Here, we focus on two aspects of this organism: the perception of an atmosphere and the resulting emotional response. The perceived atmosphere of a space is considered to be a fairly stable concept because it concerns an affective evaluation of the environment rather than an affective state or feeling itself [9]. In other

words, the atmosphere is more strongly linked to the expected than the actual emotional effect of the environment. This, of course, results from the fact that the emotional condition of a person is usually determined by many factors, including several that are independent from the immediate surroundings.

In many cases, the goal of creating a certain atmosphere in a retail environment is precisely to try to elicit a certain emotional effect on the consumer. Indeed, emotions are important factors in various consumer behaviors (see [10] for a review) and more specific purchase behavior [8]. However, as there is some inconsistency on what actually constitutes an emotion [11], we will briefly outline how we interpret emotions. Firstly, emotions form a background to which cognitive judgments, preferences or attitudes operate [12,13]. Secondly, emotions are generally stronger in intensity than moods [8] and they have a clear object of referent (e.g. the store environment) [14]. Consequently, emotions and mood are separate concepts in our model and also need to be measured separately to grasp the full spectrum of emotional reactions to the retail environment.

In sum, what matters to us is how a specifically designed store is interpreted in terms of the perceived atmosphere, the emotions elicited by that store, the mediating role of the pre-existing mood of a consumer in this process, and finally the relation with the aforementioned resulting behavior. For example, when consumers perceive a space as more ‘cozy’ and more ‘pleasant’, do they also experience more pleasure? And do they tend to stay longer in this environment or buy more products? Next, we address how the abstract concepts of Stimulus, Organism and Response can actually be translated into real-life conceptions.

3. Put into practice

In experimental research based on our conceptual research model, designers play the crucial role of selecting or creating relevant stimuli (S) because the process is approached from the experience of the environment as a whole. This designers’ holistic perspective implies a need to conduct experiments in a real three-dimensional retail setting in which observers can stay and move about. Of course, as 3D retail environments that allow manipulation of environmental cues and registering effects on visitors are not readily available, we have constructed a “Retail design research lab”, which is a modular, fully modifiable room with a one-way-mirror and three observation cameras.

Next, we need to be able to measure aspects of the organism (O), that is, a consumer’s internal responses. Firstly, to measure the interpretation of space, we adapted an instrument developed by Vogels [9], who proposed a tool to quantify the perceived atmosphere of an environment. It consists of 38 atmospheric descriptors, of which participants are asked to indicate the level of applicability on a seven-point Likert scale. The tool was shown to be a robust and sensitive measure. Secondly, the emotions elicited by the store are measured with the use of the Pleasure, Arousal, and Dominance-model (PAD) of Mehrabian and Russell [15] as it was adapted to the study of store atmospherics by Donovan and Rossiter [16]. Brengman [17] and Machleit and Eroglu [18] both conducted a thorough literature review to compare relevant emotion measuring instruments. Their findings suggest that this model offers the most suitable tools in measuring emotions in retail environments when the focus of interest lies on the architectural and atmospheric features. Petermans [19] confirmed this after conducting an experiment comparing several emotional measurement instruments. With the PAD-questionnaire, each of the three emotional dimensions is measured via six semantic differential items. Each item consists of a seven-point scale with opposing emotional words at either end (e.g., happy - unhappy). We currently use a Dutch translation, validated by Brengman while investigating the influence of color in retail environments [17]. Thirdly, we

measure pre-existing mood via the MSF (mood short form), a short mood questionnaire that consists of four questions and is widely used in psychological research [20]. An important point of discussion in the literature is the most appropriate time to measure mood. As suggested by several researchers, more research should be undertaken with regard to this moment [16,21,22]. So far, research focused on measuring both emotions and mood only after seeing the retail environment, as was outlined by Mehrabian and Russell [15]. However, given the possible effect of mood on the interpretation of space [23], we opted to measure emotions after the shop experience and mood prior to entering the store.

Finally, as mentioned, the actual, overt response behavior (R) can be registered as well. We try to develop an understanding of the complete spectrum of shopping behavior and therefore include purchase behavior (what consumers buy) and browsing behavior (how consumers behave inside the store). To assess behavior we observe participants' actions during the actual shop experience, rather than asking what they would do (intended behavior). By giving the participant in our experiment an assignment, such as buying groceries for a two-person breakfast, they actually experience the retail environment holistically and they also behave in a certain way (browsing behavior, buying behavior). As the lab is equipped with a one-way screen and multiple cameras, all overt, in-store browsing behavior can be observed and recorded (e.g., route taken, walking speed, time spent) and buying behavior can be measured by registering the consumers' actual purchases (e.g., number of products, type of products, amount spent).

We acknowledge that this type of research approach has limitations due to the holistic nature of space and architecture [6]. However, we do believe that when conducted carefully and with an informative selection of appropriate stimuli in our lab, we can come to a better comprehension of consumers' emotions in relation to perceived space and the resulting behavior.

4. Experiment

4.1 Store design

Although many atmospheric features, either individually or integrated, exert influence on emotions in retail environments, our research concerns a single element due to its practicality of controlling and manipulating in our lab. Moreover, one variable can be used to attribute and isolate a possible influence on the organism. Since we were looking for a simple elicitation of different atmospheres by changing a single stimulus, our focus shifted to lighting. Lighting is an important aspect of a store's interior, and it has not yet received the attention it deserves [24]. Moreover, lighting is acknowledged to have an incremental added value to the retail environment, store branding and maybe even customer binding [25]. Additionally, it is interesting to see whether one aspect of a retail environment, which does not even get the necessary attention in the design process, can influence and change the perception of a store's atmosphere. Therefore, an experiment is set-up in our lab to research the influence of different lighting conditions on perceived atmosphere, emotional state, the resulting behavior, and the possible correlations between them, as visualized in Figure 2.

Figure.2 Research model with four outlined stages

Because interviews with experts [25] showed that there was a clear need for research in lighting food, the lab was set-up as a mini-supermarket. To make the supermarket appear as typical as possible, racks and gondolas of real supermarket suppliers were used. Furthermore, seven food categories with real and fresh products were presented (Figure 3). The signage was kept minimal but functional and the products were ‘priced’ with credits to complete the “natural” supermarket experience.

Figure.3 Floor plan lab-supermarket showing seven food-categories, three cameras and two interview rooms

As we were not interested in the specific effects of lighting attributes per se, the lighting settings that were used were not the result of systematically manipulating some physical characteristics, such as a simple linear increase of the overall lighting level for example. Instead, three specific lighting settings were carefully designed to simulate lighting settings of three different supermarkets of different segmentations in Belgium: one high quality supermarket (Delhaize), one discounter (Carrefour), and a hard discounter (Aldi). Therefore, the lighting of these supermarkets was measured in terms of luminance (Lux) and the color temperature was identified (dependent on

lamp type). Furthermore, the balance between general lighting and accent lighting could play a crucial role in the atmosphere of a supermarket. Therefore, this was also taken into consideration while designing the three look-alike atmospheres for our lab. Consequently, the general lighting of the high quality setting and the hard discounter setting has a color temperature of 3000 Kelvin (which is more ‘warm’ white light); the discounter setting has a color temperature of 4000 Kelvin (which is more ‘cold’ white light). The three settings as used with their Lux-levels and the type of accent lighting are shown in Table 1. The corresponding light plans and photographs are shown in Figure 4.

Table 1. Overview of the luminance and lamps for each setting, based on the corresponding supermarket

Lux	Groceries	Dairy	Bread	Cosmetics	Wine	Fruit & Veg
High quality	978	1188	437	397	241	1193
Discounter	1064	1276	534	1109	884	1620
Hard discounter	452	640	452	452	452	452
Accent lighting	Groceries	Dairy	Bread	Cosmetics	Wine	Fruit & Veg
High quality	Non	TL830	TL830 shelves & CDM830 spot	TL830 shelves	CDM930	SDW930
Discounter	Non	TL840	TL830 shelves	TL830 shelves	SDW825	CDM930 (F) & CDM942 (V)
Hard discounter	Non	TL830	Non	Non	Non	Non

Figure.4 Floor plans with corresponding photographs (high quality supermarket, discounter and hard discounter)

4.2 Experimental set-up

During two weeks, 90 people took part in the experiment. Without knowing what the study was about, they were provided with a specific, realistic shopping scenario: buying breakfast for two people with the possibility to buy products that the participant needed that day (impulse purchases). A budget of 50 credits was given to complete the holistic shopping experience. This budget was set high enough that it did not force the participants to make

specific product choices to fit the budget. Furthermore, participants were tested alone and were asked to behave as they would in ‘normal’ shopping circumstances. Prior to the shopping task, the participant needed to fill in the mood questionnaire and answer questions about gender, age, education level, income level, shopping frequency, the places shopped for groceries (market, specialized stores, supermarket; six different supermarkets chains present in Belgium), left- or right- handedness and family composition. During the shop experience the participant was observed and the selected products were scanned. After the completion of the shopping task the participant was asked to fill in the atmosphere questionnaire in the lab supermarket. Finally, the PAD-questionnaire (measuring elicited emotions), a questionnaire about the perceived image of the supermarket-lab and some questions about the impulse purchases, were asked in one of the interview rooms.

4.3 Results

As indicated in Figure 3, the results will be explained in four stages.

1) Does lighting have an impact on how the supermarket’s atmosphere is perceived?

The questionnaire used to assess how atmosphere was perceived consisted of 38 different items. The individual items that differed most strongly (i.e., that were larger than a pre-defined cut-off point) between the three lighting settings can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Most differing individual items

	High quality versus Discounter	High quality versus Hard discounter	Discounter versus Hard discounter
Increase	Hospitable Warm Contemporary Cozy	Warm Cozy Inspiring	Mysterious
Decrease	Dull Bleak	Fidgety Dull Old fashioned Bleak	

It seems that the strongest differences can be found for the high quality store compared to the other two. In addition to investigating individual items, previous research [9] has also shown that the atmosphere questionnaire can be split up in four subscales which allows for distinguishing between four different atmosphere dimensions: coziness (consisting of items such as ‘cozy’, ‘warm’, ‘pleasant’, ...), liveliness (‘lively’, ‘stimulating’, ...), tenseness (‘tense’, ‘uncomfortable’, ‘threatening’,...) and detachment (‘detached’, ‘formal’, ...). Although in general the differences between the three settings are not very large for these four atmosphere dimensions, the ‘high quality’ store does score the highest on coziness and liveliness and the lowest on tenseness and detachment. So, the perception of the atmosphere of a particular retail environment seems to be affected by the lighting setting in that environment. Does this difference in perceived atmosphere also lead to a recognition of the supermarkets on which the settings were based? Figure 5 demonstrates that this seems to be at least partially true, as the high quality (Delhaize) setting was also recognized as such.

Figure.5 Perception of each atmosphere

Moreover, the results of the questions about price perception, quality and service level show that for each of these attributes the ‘high quality’ store also received the highest score, which is consistent with the corporate image of that particular retailer. The other two stores, however, were not recognized consistently. A possible explanation for the non-recognition of the hard discounter might simply be that the specific racks and gondolas in our lab are quite different from the ones that are usually present in those stores. Nevertheless, it appears that even with only a relatively subtle difference in lighting, an otherwise identical supermarket environment can indeed be given a different, or even very specific, atmosphere.

2) Do different perceived atmospheres in a store also elicit different emotional responses in the consumer?

The analysis of the results of the PAD-questionnaire, used to assess the amount of Pleasure, Arousal and Dominance experienced in the store, showed that there were no consistent differences for the ‘dominance’ or the ‘arousal’ factor for the three lighting settings. However, the scores for ‘pleasure’ were clearly increased for the high quality setting compared to the other settings, indicating that this store elicited more positive feelings in consumers. In addition, we also checked whether there was a link between how a consumer perceived the atmosphere in terms of coziness, liveliness, tenseness and detachment, and how the same consumer reacted emotionally, in terms of how much pleasure and arousal the store elicited. As could be expected, experienced pleasure increased when the perceived coziness and liveliness increased. Similarly, when a store was interpreted as more tense and more detached, the experienced pleasure went down. On the other hand, the perceived atmosphere did not seem to be connected to how much arousal the consumer experienced. In other words, in the present experiment, the type of feelings brought about by the store, i.e., a positive versus a negative emotional response, was linked to the perceived atmosphere, but the intensity of those feelings, i.e. the arousal they experienced, was not.

3) Is there an influence of the pre-existing mood on the perceived atmosphere and the elicited emotional response?

Before entering the store, all participants filled in a mood questionnaire. On average, these mood scores were very similar for the three groups that saw the three different lighting settings, so the difference in results on perceived atmosphere and emotional response can not be explained by a difference in mood. However, it is still possible to investigate whether, across participants, a change in individual mood score changes how the atmosphere is perceived or how customers respond to the store emotionally. Somewhat surprisingly, we did not

find a strong connection between the mood score and any of the scores on the three emotional dimensions (P-A-D). In other words, the pleasure or arousal elicited by the store was not necessarily higher for consumers who entered the store in a better mood. Concerning the perceived atmosphere, there does seem to be a slight effect, as people in a better mood tend to perceive the atmosphere as less tense. On the whole, however, our results suggest that, in the present experiment, the mood people were in before they entered the store did not readily affect how they perceived the store, nor how they responded emotionally to the store.

4) Do the different lighting settings have an effect on the resulting behavior?

Little difference in behavioral response was found for the three settings. Even the comparison between the high quality setting and the other two gave no clear results: contrary to expectations regarding the influence of emotions on purchase behavior (as stated in some research [1-3]), the higher degree of experienced pleasure in the high quality setting, did not translate into a significant increase in browsing behavior or buying behavior. The only behavioral aspect that was somewhat consistent with the results of the atmosphere and the PAD questionnaire was a trend in the time spent shopping. The high quality setting scored the highest on ‘coziness’ and ‘liveliness’ and an increased pleasure was measured, so it could be expected that consumers would also tend to stay longer. It was also found that the discount setting had the shortest average shopping time of 143 seconds, the hard discount setting came second with an average time of 164 seconds, and the high quality setting had the longest shopping time with 173 seconds. Nevertheless, it appears that the different lighting settings did not have a large impact on the final behavior of our participants.

4.4 Summary

Although the current experiment is an implementation of conducting experimental research from a ‘designerly’ perspective, the results are promising. It appears that even a relatively subtle difference in lighting, an otherwise identical supermarket environment can be given a different, or even very specific, atmosphere. This confirms the importance of creating a suitable atmosphere, even for a basic product such as food. Furthermore, perceived atmosphere seems to have an influence on elicited emotions at least for the Pleasure dimension, but not for the intensity of those feelings (Arousal). Moreover, the mood people were in before they entered the store did not readily affect how they perceived the store, nor how they responded emotionally to the store. Finally, no significant results were found regarding the resulting behavior. So, in our research model, stage 1 and 2 are confirmed, but 3 and 4 lack of significant results.

5. Discussion

Following the S-O-R model, we have looked at the response of consumers, in terms of mood, emotions, actual behavior and their interaction, to a certain environmental stimulus. In this model, we assumed the emotions to be a consequence of the perceived space. However, there remains the possibility that this is in fact a complex interaction in which the emotions also influence how the space itself is interpreted. This mechanism is difficult to trace and it is most certainly not the ambition to do so in the current paper. Rather, the present study should be seen as an example of how experimental research on retail design and emotions can be performed. In addition to classic methodological concerns, in this type of “research from a designerly perspective” the use of relevant and informative manipulations and actual 3D environments allowing for a holistic experience of the space are crucial.

Finally, although specific behavioral reactions were not immediately found, we do believe that creating a specific store experience by changing the atmosphere through an environmental manipulation such as lighting can have clear benefits in the long term. Not only were the participants able to recognize different atmospheres, they also scored them accordingly concerning quality and price perception, which are highly relevant aspects when it comes to store branding and store personality. This way, these results once again underline the importance of every little aspect of a store's environment.

6. References

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